

than 80%. Many types of pollen strains combined the two parents' traits, with variation ranging close to that of F₂ progenies.

The stability of BB resistance and of other agricultural traits were analyzed in H₃ and H₄ (see table). In pollen plants, these were all relatively stable in different generations. In stable H₂ pollen strains, the resistance capability and character uniformities did not vary with generation advance (H₃ and H₄).

We concluded that the anther culture method effectively transfers the resistance gene. □

Stability of pollen strain resistance to bacterial blight.

Cross	Generation	Strain no.	Lesion area ^a (%)	Strain no.	Lesion area ^b (%)
Shennong 1033/Zenith	H ₂	89-3710	3.0 ± 0.2	89-3724	16.7 ± 1.6
	H ₃		2.0 ± 1.8		16.8 ± 1.4
	H ₄		2.3 ± 0.1		15.7 ± 1.4
Shennong 1033/75-34	H ₂	89-3841	4.7 ± 0.2	89-3873	14.5 ± 0.8
	H ₃		4.7 ± 0.2		14.7 ± 1.2
	H ₄		4.9 ± 0.1		15.7 ± 1.4
Shennong 1033/Java 14	H ₂	89-3753	2.9 ± 0.2	89-3924	14.0 ± 1.3
	H ₃		4.9 ± 0.1		13.3 ± 1.6
	H ₄		4.9 ± 0.1		12.8 ± 1.2
Shennong 1033/Pei Zhao 15	H ₂	89-3795	4.9 ± 0.1	89-3819	14.9 ± 1.1
	H ₃		4.9 ± 0.1		13.9 ± 1.2
	H ₄		4.9 ± 0.1		14.1 ± 1.1

^aAll values are equivalent to R (resistant). ^bAll values are equivalent to MR (moderately resistant).

Resistance to sheath blight (ShB) and brown spot (BS) in lines derived from *Oryza officinalis*

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We evaluated 87 breeding lines derived from *O. officinalis* for resistance to ShB caused by *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk, and BS caused by *Cochliobolus miyabeanus* (Ito & Kuribayashi) Drechsler ex Dastur.

In the field, one row per line and check TKM9 were transplanted at 30 × 15-cm in 3-m-long plots, in a randomized block with three replications.

We assessed ShB weekly and BS biweekly from active tillering to the milk stage, using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES). Lines completely free from ShB and BS were artificially inoculated for further evaluation.

Disease incidence was evaluated in the greenhouse by stem tape inoculation for ShB and spore suspension spray for BS, on 21 seedlings/line. Actively tillering plants were inoculated with 20-d-old ShB pathogen cultured on autoclaved rice stem pieces, inserted into the sheaths, 5 cm above the water line. For BS inoculation, plants were sprayed with a 10⁷ conidia/ml suspension.

Disease severity was assessed every 7 d for ShB and every 10 d for BS from the

Lines derived from *O. officinalis* showing resistance to ShB and BS.

Intensity (0-9 scale)	Lines	
	ShB	BS
1 (highly resistant)	IR54742-6-1-14-15-3 IR54742-33-18-20-3-2 IR54745-2-10-17-8-3 IR54745-2-23-19-8-2 IR54742-1-11-17-12-3	IR54742-1-11-17-26-1 IR54742-1-17-20-8-3 IR54742-33-9-14-26-4 IR54742-33-18-20-3-1 IR54742-33-18-20-3-2 IR54742-38-13-15-11-1 IR54745-2-10-17-8-1 IR54745-2-21-12-17-4 IR54745-2-23-19-8-1 IR54745-2-23-19-18-2
3 (resistant)	IR54742-1-11-17-12-1 IR54742-1-11-17-12-3 IR54742-1-11-17-26-2 IR54742-6-20-3-9-3 IR54742-11-1-9-15-1 IR54742-33-9-14-26-4 IR54745-2-21-12-17-4 IR54745-2-34-3-10-2 IR54751-3-38-10-15-3 IR54742-50-19-19-1-1 IR54742-50-19-19-1-3	IR54742-1-11-17-12-1 IR54742-1-11-17-12-3 IR54742-1-19-11-8-2 IR54742-6-20-3-22-3 IR54742-6-20-9-3-2 IR54742-11-22-2-22-2 IR54742-18-17-20-15-1 IR54742-22-14-24-22-3 IR54742-22-19-3-7-3 IR54742-31-9-26-15-2 IR54742-33-18-20-3-2 IR54745-2-10-17-8-3 IR54745-2-21-12-17-5 IR54745-2-34-3-10-2
9 (highly susceptible)	TKM9 (check)	TKM9

time symptoms appeared on the susceptible check until the milk stage.

Under natural infection, 87 and 48 of the derived lines were ShB- and BS-free.

Under artificial inoculation, 5 lines were highly resistant to ShB and 10 to BS (see table). □

Resistance to sheath rot (ShR) of breeding lines derived from *Oryza officinalis*

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We evaluated 87 breeding lines derived from *O. officinalis* for resistance to ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams & Hawksw.

Twenty plants for each derived line were transplanted into 1-row, 3-m-long plots spaced at 30 × 15 cm. Beds were laid out in randomized blocks with three replications. From booting stage onward,

we evaluated disease intensity weekly with the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES). IR20 served as the susceptible check.

In the greenhouse, disease-free lines were artificially inoculated using two methods. We inoculated one set of lines with a 15-d-old, single-grain culture in between the flag leaf sheath and the unemerged panicle.

In the other set, rice mealy bugs (*Brevinnia rehi* Lindinger) were mass-reared using 45-d-old TN1 rice. Crawlers were collected and soaked in *S. oryzae* spore suspension for 15 min (10^7 conidia/ml). Crawlers were placed in between the flag leaf sheath and the unemerged panicle using a camel hair brush.

Fifteen derived lines were completely disease-free under natural infection, only a few lines exhibited high resistance under artificial methods (see table). The check had maximum disease severity under all conditions. □

Reactions of derived *O. officinalis* lines to SHR.

Intensity (0-9 scale)	Designation	
	Single-grain inoculation	Mealy bug inoculation
1 (highly resistant)	IR54742-6-34-17-11-1	IR54742-6-34-17-11-1
	IR54742-18-3-8-22-1	IR54742-18-3-8-22-1
	IR54742-22-14-3-7-2	IR54742-22-14-3-7-2
	IR54742-22-19-3-7-1	IR54745-2-21-12-17-1
	IR54742-33-9-14-26-3	
	IR54742-33-18-20-3-2	
	IR54742-33-37-16-10-1	
	IR54745-2-21-12-17-1	
	IR54751-1-19-13-17-1	
	IR54742-22-14-24-22-3	IR54742-22-14-24-22-3
3 (resistant)	IR54742-31-21-20-10-3	IR54742-22-19-3-7-1
	IR54742-22-19-3-7-3	IR54742-33-9-14-26-3
	IR54742-2-21-12-17-5	IR54742-33-18-20-3-2
		IR54742-33-37-16-10-1
7 (susceptible)	IR54742-33-18-20-3-1	-
	IR54745-2-10-17-8-3	
9 (highly susceptible)	-	IR54742-22-19-3-7-3
		IR54742-31-21-20-10-3
		IR54742-33-18-20-3-1
		IR54745-2-16-17-8-3
		IR54745-2-21-12-17-5

Pest resistance — insects

Resistance of rice varieties to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) in the greenhouse

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We screened 916 new rice varieties and breeding lines during 1986-90 for resistance to WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* by using the bulk seedling test. Test entries were sown in 20-cm rows in plastic seedboxes at 20 seeds/row. Each entry had three replications.

Seedlings were infested 7 d after sowing with second- to third-instar WBPH nymphs at 6-8 nymphs/seedling. Plant damage was scored when all plants of susceptible check TN1 had died.

Ninety of the test entries showed resistance to WBPH (see table).

Resistance of rice varieties to WBPH in the greenhouse. China. 1986-90.

Variety	Damage score ^a	Variety	Damage score ^a
Shanyougui 8	3	Liaoyanru no. 4	3
Bangriai 7	3	C710	3
84570	3	Mingdao 580	3
84547	3	Wanqingzao no. 2	1
Chuangmi no. 1	3	Sanluzhan no. 7	3
Chuangmi no. 2	3	883016	3
8603	3	Zhong 86-44	3
8604	1	Zhong 86-51	1
2314	3	Zhongyu 88-6	3
851193	3	Zhongyu 88-9	3
851515	3	3123	3
851633	3	Jiangyou 594	3
853161	1	85-151	3
853209	3	Wanhui 500065	1
352	1	50239	3
Qishuangzhan	0	Nanjing 58156	1
Xiangzheng 21	1	6267	3
85-2-591	1	Dan42-1	3
Guangye 90	1	Shuangerai	3
7526-4	3	Fu 8329	3
1296	3	Fu 8456	1
Sixizhan	3	Fu 8531	3
Zhehu no. 1	3	V20 A x Pinghui no. 2	3
E3-14	3	Ping 10	3
E3-57	3	H8702	3
E3-147	3	86013	3
Jing15	3	46-204	1
Nonghu no. 3	3	HA8517	1
Dianrui 138	1	HA85-183	0
Dianrui 236	1	V49	1
H11	3	V20 A x 1126	3
Liaoyan 283	3	Yuwanfu no. 5	1

continued on next page